

TECHNICAL NOTE

Simulation of oil slick drift with the PETROMAR-3D model in case of offshore spills in waters adjacent to the Brazilian northeast.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5579816>

Abstract

This technical note presents the graphical outputs of the lagrangian model PETROMAR-3D, version 2.1G, specialized to assume the operative work before real spills and to obtain statistical results before climatic executions. The scenarios were created in the waters adjacent to the Brazilian NE, with simulation times of thirty days, every 3 hours in the most representative months of each season of the year. The numerical simulations were focused to characterize the oil drift, taking 3 starting points located at (30°W, 6°S), (30°W, 7°S) and (30°W, 8°S). As initial and boundary conditions the surface currents of the HYCOM (global domain 3-hourly and 1/12 degree analysis) hydrodynamic model were used and for the spill a light crude oil of 35 API (849 kg m⁻³) and initial volumes of 3145 bb (500 m³) were considered. As main results, it was found that the spills located at point 1 had the fastest drifts and in many cases, the slick continued to the north. Those with starting point 2 had slower drifts, but with moderate impacts on the coast, and finally, the spills starting from point 3 had the slowest drifts of all cases, however, they concentrated the most severe impacts on the adjacent coastal sectors. In January and October, they have the most severe impacts and in October they have the fastest drifts, an event that should be taken into account by decision-makers, to have more effective responses for these cases.

Keywords: Oil slick drift, HYCOM model, PETROMAR-3D model, Offshore spills, Brazilian northeast.

1.0. Introduction

Since the industrial revolution, fossil fuels have been the foundation of modern and contemporary society. The growth in population demand for energy sources, products and services leads to the expansion of Oil Exploration and Production (E&P) and the number of vessels circulating the oceans transporting fuels and other products and, consequently, the potential risk of oil pollution in the sea.

The knowledge of the trajectory of oil slicks through Oceanography is of fundamental importance for the estimation of potential risks as well as for the development of contingency plans, in which the application of numerical modeling makes it possible to predict the displacement of oil slicks, allowing better effectiveness in acting forms of the contingency processes.

The general objective of this work was to provide a tool capable of predicting the scattering of hydrocarbons along the western edge of the Tropical Atlantic, using the combination of data analysis and mathematical modeling techniques capable of representing coastal, oceanic dynamics and water processes. dispersion and transformation of hydrocarbons over the tropical South Atlantic adjacent to the Northeast region of Brazil. The approach adopted to achieve this objective is based on the analysis of past data obtained in situ, on the use of oceanographic observation and reanalysis databases, and the crossing/comparison of these data with the application of the results obtained for the thermodynamic fields in Lagrangian numerical simulations of oil dispersion.

2.0. Material and Methods

2.1. Study area

The Brazilian Equatorial Margin is a region that encompasses the coastal, shelf and oceanic zones adjacent to the North and Northeast regions of Brazil, extending from Sergipe to Amapá. It is a region of economic importance for artisanal fishing and expressive wealth in terms of biodiversity (Figure 1).

The climate in the region is warm tropical with an average temperature of 25°C and well-defined dry season between August and February and rainy season between March and July, with an average annual rainfall of 1400 mm (Serafini and França, 2010). The maximum average insolation occurs in November and the minimum in April (IBAMA, 2005).

The strongest seasonal signal for the region is modulated by the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), which reaches its southernmost position between February and March and northernmost position in August (Lumpkin and Garzoli, 2005; Stramma and Schott, 1999). The prevailing winds are the southeast trade winds, with greater intensities between July and August. The highest sea surface temperatures (SST) occur between March and June, with values above 28°C, and the lowest between August and November, (SST ~26.5°C) (Hounsou-Gbo et al., 2015; Tchamabi et al., 2017).

On the surface, the central branch of the South Equatorial Current (cSEC) that flows westward until it reaches the North Brazil Current (NBC) near the coast influences the region (Lumpkin and Garzoli, 2005; Stramma and Schott, 1999). Drifter and model results shows that the cSEC has a Strong signal between March and July and a weaker signal between August and February (Tchamabi et al., 2017).

The Southwestern Tropical Atlantic Ocean (SWTA) region is controlled by a complex system of surface and subsurface currents into the mixed layer (Stramma and Schott, 1999). The South Equatorial Current (SEC) is the main current in this region (Stramma and Schott, 1999). The central branch of SEC (cSEC) is located between the South Equatorial Undercurrent (Fig.1; SEUC), and the South Equatorial Counter Current (SECC), showing low salinities in the surface (around 36) over the others nearby currents (Bonou et al., 2017). Around 3°-5°S, west of 35° W (western boundary system), the cSEC forms the Northern Brazil Undercurrent and North Brazilian Current system (NBUC/NBC).

The southernmost branch is the southern SEC (sSEC), which flows to the west and is fed by Benguela Current. It transports salty and relatively cold waters (Fig.1). Previous studies suggest that it bifurcates between 10° S and 20° S, near Brazilian continental shelf (Peterson and Stramma, 1991), but there is a variability transport that can be related with a possible variation seasonal and/or annual (Bonou et al., 2017).

Towards the north, at 12-14°S, the sSEC feeds the NBUC/NBC (Lumpkin and Garzoli, 2005), along with northward cSEC. South of 12°S, a small part of the sSEC becomes the Brazil Current (BC), as the western current band of the subtropical gyre (Peterson and Stramma, 1991).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of surface (solid line) and subsurface (dashed line) currents along the Tropical Atlantic between 30°N–30°S and 60°W–15°E, with highlighted study area (adapted from Stramma; Schott, 1999).

The main surface and subsurface water masses of the SWTA are Tropical Surface Water (TSW) and South Atlantic Central Water (SACW), respectively. This first mass is characterized as warm, with temperatures about 27° C and salinity of 36, occupying the surface mixed layer. Its lower limit is near the 20° C isotherm, at about 50 m (Peterson and Stramma, 1991). Underneath, the SACW, circulates in the subtropical gyre.

2.2. General Model Design. Physical and Mathematical Basis of the Model.

The computational tool used to carry out the simulations was the Lagrangian model PETROMAR-3D, version 2.1G. The model presented represents the scattering of a slick or plume of contaminant launched through a source in a body of water, with the velocity field calculated using the hydrodynamic mathematical model. The geographic launch points are indicated in table 1.

Figure 2. The study region (blue square) indicates the starting points of the simulation (red-dot P1; blue-dot P2; black-dot P3). The color sidebar indicates the bathymetry in the region.

Table 1. Geographic coordinates of launch points.

Identification	Geographic coordinates
P1	30°W; 6°S
P2	30°W, 7°S
P3	30°W, 8°S

The PETROMAR-3D model, version 2.1, was created at the Marine Meteorology Center of the Cuban Meteorological Institute. This Lagrangian model was designed to describe the physical processes of marine oil spills in the face of multiple marine environment scenarios; although it applies to any part of the world, it is primarily designed for the inter-American seas.

This model describes physical processes as follows:

If the spill occurs on the sea surface, the runoff is calculated according to Fay's equations (Liu et al. 2013; Calzada et al. 2021), to then decompose the slick into virtual particles and carry out the advection and diffusion processes.

Advection is calculated considering marine currents and wind, while diffusion, a Brownian motion is simulated using the random walk method (Spaulding, 2017).

Taking these processes into account, the motion of the partial particles was assumed through three numerical schemes: Euler (E), second-order Runge Kutta (RK2) and fourth-order (RK4); each one with its characteristics, precisions and requirements. The interaction with the shoreline is analyzed in a first approximation, as there is no differentiation of the shoreline type. Despite this, there is great precision in the calculation of the time each of the parts that make up the pollutant reaches the coast.

At the same time, the processes of evaporation (with the PC method), vertical dispersion (with the proposal of Delvigne and Sweeney) and emulsification (via Eley's law of change) are calculated (from the beginning). All this combination of processes favors those time-based parameters such as density, viscosity, thickness and concentration of the oil slick can be calculated.

If the spill occurs deep in the sea, the model will run similarly, except for two main aspects: the oil scattering on the surface will be the result of the radius value of the plume around its axis. The parameters of the spot position and dimension are described in the blowout process. Another aspect is that the pollutant density and viscosity values in the surface movement will be linked to the upward movement, introduced by the method proposed by Zheng et al. (2003).

The system will work in four steps:

- 1) Selection and interpretation of data.
- 2) Creation of scenarios (framed by dates, zones and supplier models, from a configuration file that allows the entry of initial parameters.
- 3) Calculation of the trajectory considering the initial coordinates (X, Y, Z), the spilled volume or the spill rate, the oil type and other aerial or satellite information are also initialized within a configuration file.
- 4) The graphical representations and storage of numerical data of the results are tasks performed through Matplotlib and Basemap libraries.

The Lagrangian method for describing the processes in the spot causes the concentration to be calculated indirectly. In this work, the surface marine currents of the HYCOM model with 1/12° resolution were used, with a time interval of 3 hours.

The HYCOM (HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model) is an ocean circulation model with primitive equations that combines three types of vertical coordinates (Cartesian, sigma and isopycnal), this allows to better study the mixing layer and to handle very well the interaction between layers of different densities (Chassignet et al., 2007); it has an hourly output and a spatial resolution of 1/12° which makes this analysis product a good product to use its surface currents as initial and boundary conditions into PETROMAR-3D model. Ten years have been taken to make the hourly climatology (2003 - 2012) which was used as input in the PETROMAR-3D model. As bathymetry, we have used GEBCO (IOC, IHO and BODC, 2003) which has a resolution of 15 s of arc.

2.3. Temperature and salinity

The sea surface temperature and salinity data (SST and SSS, respectively) were obtained from the database: Global Ocean Physical Reanalysis product GLOBAL_REANALYSIS (Fernandez and Lellouche, 2018). The representative months of each climatic period (January, April, July and October) analyzed are shown in figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3. SST at the western edge of the South Tropical Atlantic Ocean. The 4 months represent the months corresponding to the climatic periods: boreal winter (January), boreal spring (April), boreal summer (July), and boreal autumn (October).

Figure 4. SST at the western edge of the South Tropical Atlantic Ocean. The 4 months represent the months corresponding to the climatic periods: boreal winter (January), boreal spring (April), boreal summer (July), and boreal autumn (October).

3.0. Results and discussion

This section shows the results of oil spill simulations in three points in the northeast region of Brazil. The temporal analyzes of these simulations were carried out in four months of the year (January, April, July and October) which correspond to the representative months of the 4 climatic periods characteristic of this region.

The simulation results for January (point P1; figure 5a) indicated that the oil slick reaches the coastline at latitude 4.1°S, while the oil slick also reaches latitude 6.7°S (State of Pernambuco, Brazil). The launch at point P2 (Figure 5b) of the simulation reaches the region south of 6.7°S, positioning itself at an angle of approximately 45° with the shoreline. Unlike points P1 and P2, the launch from point P3 (Figure 5c) does not approach the coastal region, indicating the strong influence of currents in this region.

Figure 5. Oil slick drift simulations in January for the three points indicated in table 1.

During the boreal spring period (April), point P1 (Figure 6a) shows a similar trajectory to figure 5a of the same point in January, while the release of point P2 (Figure 6b) covers an extensive area of northeastern Brazil, Brazil without reaching the coastline. The launch from point P3 (Figure 6c) does not reach the shore, being confined between 8-9°S.

Figure 6. Oil slick drift simulations in April for the three points indicated in table 1.

In July, the launch from point P1 reaches the coastal region at latitude 4.1°S (Figure 7a), similar to the launch from point P2 (Figure 7b). Figure 7c shows the trajectory of the launch from point P3, reaching the shore at 5°S, and covering a latitudinal band of approximately 5° very close to

the shoreline. The oil slick moves away from the coastal region at latitudes 8-9°S.

Figure 7. Oil slick drift simulations in July for the three points indicated in table 1.

During October (Figure 8a) the launch from point P1 reaches the shoreline at 4°S, similar to point P2 (Figure 8b) which follows a trajectory in the same direction, but without reaching the shoreline. An opposite direction follows the launch from point P3 (Figure 8c), which hits 3 areas on the shoreline between 7-9.3°S.

Figure 8. Oil slick drift simulations in October for the three points indicated in table 1.

In general, the launch from point P1, reaches higher speeds when compared to other points. The drift from point P3 showed slower drifts; however, the impacted area is larger. The temporal analysis showed that in January and October the impacts are more severe, reaching larger areas in the northeast region of Brazil.

4.0. Final considerations

The results of oil spill simulations in three points in the northeast region of Brazil through the PETROMAR-3D model showed spatial and temporal variations according to the launch point and climatic period of the region.

In general, launches from point P1 reach the northern region with a faster drift, product of the current intensities in the study region, different from launches from point P2, but with a larger impact area.

The drifts from point P3 showed slower drifts when compared to the drifts from points P1 and; however, impacts are more severe in the adjacent coastal region.

The temporal analysis showed that the most severe impacts occurred in January and October. In this last month, trajectory drifts were the fastest, when compared to the other months analyzed.

The spatial and temporal analysis of this study should be considered in mitigation projects by government agencies to provide quick responses in preventing future oil spill events in the northeast region of Brazil.

5.0. Supplementary material

In the supplementary material we include the main results obtained with the PETROMAR-3D model.

Calzada, A. E., Varona, H. L., Chang, D., Rodriguez, A., Reyes, D., Noriega, C., & Araujo, M. (2021). Main results of simulation of oil slick drift with the PETROMAR-3D model in case of offshore spills in waters adjacent to the Brazilian northeast. figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.16834819>

URL:

https://figshare.com/articles/figure/Main_results_of_simulation_of_oil_slick_drift_with_the_PETROMAR-3D_model_in_case_of_offshore_spills_in_waters_adjacent_to_the_Brazilian_northeast_/16834819

6.0. Acknowledgment:

Carlos Noriega thanks to Human Resources Program of the Brazilian National Petroleum Agency, PRH-ANP n°38, for the postdoctoral scholarship, process number 044819.

Humberto L. Varona and Moacyr Araujo thank to TRIATLAS project (Tropical and South Atlantic climate-based marine ecosystem predictions for sustainable management) and the Brazilian Research Network on Global Climate Change (Rede CLIMA).

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